

Bridging Reading Gaps Through Differentiated Visual Aids Instruction

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ABSTRACT

Visual schedules were implemented to enhance reading comprehension, vocabulary, and phonological awareness among inclusive learners in multi-school settings in Bohol and Cebu, Philippines. Pre-intervention assessments revealed that most learners scored at beginner levels in comprehension and vocabulary, with moderate skills in phonological awareness, reflecting challenges related to attention, task organization, and neurodevelopmental barriers aligned with national Phil-IRI data. Post-intervention results demonstrated significant improvements, with the majority reaching intermediate to advanced proficiency across all three reading domains and complete elimination of beginner-level scores. Statistical analysis confirmed that visual schedules effectively scaffolded comprehension, lexical processing, and phonemic skills, addressing foundational literacy deficits among learners with diverse needs. This evidence supports integrating visual schedules into DepEd's 2025–2026 inclusive literacy framework as a scalable, effective pedagogical intervention. Recommendations include formal curriculum incorporation, educator training, creation of culturally relevant visual materials, and multi-sensory instructional strategies to sustain literacy gains for inclusive learners.

KEYWORDS: *Special Education, Visual Schedules, Inclusive Learners, Reading Comprehension, Vocabulary Development, Phonological Awareness, Literacy Intervention, Neurodiverse Education, Inclusive Education, Visual Scaffolding, Pretest-Posttest Design.*

1. THE PROBLEM AND ITS SCOPE

INTRODUCTION

Rationale of the Study

Reading comprehension is a foundational skill in literacy development and a crucial component of academic success across grade levels. However, many inclusive learners-particularly those with learning difficulties, attention deficits, or neurodevelopmental disorders such as autism spectrum disorder-often struggle with maintaining focus, organizing tasks, and understanding the sequence of reading activities. These challenges can impede their ability to comprehend texts effectively. Thus, it becomes imperative for educators to employ differentiated and visually supportive teaching strategies that accommodate diverse learning needs within inclusive classrooms. One promising pedagogical approach that addresses these challenges is the use of visual schedules.

Visual schedules such as visual aids, pedagogical visual instruction, and visual supports are structured visual representations-such as charts, icons, or pictorial sequences-that outline the steps or activities involved in a lesson. They are designed to help learners understand what is expected of them and what will occur next, thereby providing predictability and reducing anxiety. According to Quintero, Baldiris, Rubira, Cerón, Velez, (2019), visual activity schedules have been shown to improve task engagement, independence, and comprehension among learners with autism spectrum disorders. In the context of reading instruction, visual schedules can serve as cognitive and organizational supports that scaffold students' understanding of text-related activities. For instance, a visual schedule may present

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the stages of a reading lesson- previewing, reading, discussing, answering comprehension questions, and reflecting-through a series of images or icons. This visual guidance allows learners to process the lesson sequence independently, promoting engagement and self-regulation.

Additionally, using visual schedules supports inclusive education by fostering a learning environment that values diversity and accessibility. Mastropieri and Scruggs (2020) emphasize that differentiated instruction strategies-such as visual and multimodal supports-are central to the success of inclusive classrooms. Visual schedules help create a predictable and inclusive learning atmosphere where students with varying abilities can participate meaningfully in reading lessons. For many learners, particularly those with special educational needs, predictability and visual structure reduce cognitive overload, increase motivation, and improve comprehension outcomes as cited in Quintero, Baldiris, Rubira, Cerón, Velez, (2019) in the study of (Dettmer et al., 2013).

On the other side, the need for locally grounded research is urgent: recent DepEd reports and school-level Phil-IRI data continue to show sizable proportions of struggling readers and low reading comprehension among Filipino learners (e.g., regionally collated Phil-IRI results reported 20% failing in reading comprehension and about 25% classified as struggling readers in the 2022–2023 cycle). Moreover, international assessments and local studies have highlighted persistent challenges in reading proficiency among Filipino students, particularly for populations who are socioeconomically disadvantaged or have special educational needs. Although research in the Philippines has explored visual learning and the use of visual aids (for example, studies on visual learning performance in Cebu and recent local investigations into visual-themed reading interventions), there is still a notable gap: few studies have systematically measured the direct effect of structured visual schedules and visual supports on reading comprehension outcomes for inclusive learners across multiple public-school contexts. By focusing on inclusive classrooms in Bohol and Cebu and employing quantitative measures of comprehension, this study addresses that gap and will produce locally relevant empirical evidence on whether - and to what extent - visual scheduling and supports improve reading comprehension and self-regulation for learners with diverse needs. The findings are expected

to contribute actionable recommendations for DepEd practice and school-level instructional planning (e.g., scalable visual-support templates, teacher training foci, and monitoring tools) that directly support inclusive literacy goals in the Philippine basic education system.

Nevertheless, the integration of visual schedules as a pedagogical tool in teaching reading comprehension provides a structured, inclusive, and learner-centered approach that supports the diverse needs of students. It empowers inclusive learners by promoting comprehension, independence, and engagement while upholding the principles of equitable education. This pedagogical practice, therefore, holds significant potential in enhancing literacy instruction and ensuring that no learner is left behind in the reading process.

Henceforth, this study aims to quantitatively assess the relationship between the application of visual schedules, visual aids, and visual supports as pedagogical strategies in selected schools in Bohol and Cebu as a basis for developing an enhanced pedagogical instructional plan for the school year 2025–2026.

Theoretical Background

This study posits that the effective implementation of visual schedules, visual aids, and visual supports as pedagogical tools can significantly improve the reading comprehension of inclusive learners, particularly in the domains of comprehension, vocabulary development, and phonological awareness.

Equally consistent to this study is anchored first on Dual Coding Theory, proposed by Allan Paivio, which explains that learning becomes more effective when information is processed through two interconnected systems: the verbal system, which manages language-based input, and the non-verbal or visual system, which handles imagery and symbolic representations. When learners receive information in both verbal and visual forms, they create dual mental representations that strengthen comprehension and memory. In reading instruction, visual schedules operationalize this theory by pairing text-based directions with images or icons that illustrate each stage of the task. This dual presentation is particularly beneficial for inclusive learners, as the visual cues reinforce verbal instructions, reduce confusion, and support students who struggle with processing lengthy or abstract verbal information.

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework of the Study

On the other side, this premise is supported by Cognitive Load Theory (CLT), which is developed by John Sweller, which emphasizes that the human working memory has limited capacity, and therefore instructional materials must be designed to prevent overload. CLT identifies intrinsic cognitive load, which relates to the complexity of the material; extraneous load, which stems from poor instructional design; and germane load, which supports meaningful learning. For learners with attention difficulties, executive-function challenges, or learning disabilities, unstructured reading tasks can create unnecessary extraneous load that hinders comprehension. Visual schedules address this by breaking reading activities into manageable steps and providing structured, predictable cues that reduce the mental effort required to plan, organize, and transition between tasks. By minimizing extraneous load, visual schedules free students' cognitive resources so they can focus more effectively on understanding the text itself.

Thirdly, the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) framework further supports the use of visual schedules in inclusive classrooms. Rooted in neuroscience, UDL advocates for designing instruction that accommodates learner variability through three core principles: providing multiple means of representation, offering multiple ways for learners to express what they know, and fostering engagement through varied motivational pathways. Visual schedules align with these principles by presenting instructional steps through accessible visual representations, ensuring that learners who may struggle with verbal instructions can still understand and participate in reading activities. They promote predictability, reduce anxiety, and enhance independence, thereby enabling students with diverse needs-including those with disabilities, processing difficulties, and language challenges-to meaningfully engage in literacy learning. Through this alignment with UDL, visual schedules

contribute to a more equitable and inclusive learning environment where all students can succeed in reading comprehension tasks.

According to Vygotsky (1978), learners construct knowledge within their *Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD)* through the assistance of more capable peers or teachers who provide scaffolds that guide learning. cognitive load, thereby optimizing the use of working memory for meaningful learning processes. load-such as decoding text or organizing information-AT tools enable students to focus their cognitive resources on understanding and integrating content. This alignment with CLT principles can enhance reading comprehension, writing skills, and overall academic performance among students with LD.

The use of visual schedules as a pedagogical approach in teaching reading comprehension for inclusive learners is anchored on several national and international laws that promote inclusive education, equitable learning opportunities, and quality literacy instruction. These legal provisions support the inclusion of all learners, regardless of ability, within mainstream classrooms and emphasize the need for differentiated and accessible instructional strategies.

At the national level, the **1987 Philippine Constitution**, Article XIV, Section 1, declares that “the State shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all.” This constitutional mandate establishes education as a right and obliges schools to provide appropriate pedagogical interventions, including the use of visual and adaptive supports, to meet diverse learners’ needs.

In alignment with this, Republic Act (RA) 11650, or the Inclusive Education Act of 2022, reinforces the Philippine government’s commitment to providing equitable and accessible education for all learners, particularly those with disabilities and other learning difficulties. The law mandates the establishment of Inclusive Learning Resource Centers in every city and municipality, promotes early identification and intervention, and ensures that learners with disabilities receive appropriate support services within regular schools. RA 11650 emphasizes the need for accessible learning materials, individualized support, and responsive pedagogical approaches that enable full participation in classroom activities. Within the context of reading instruction, the law underscores the responsibility of schools and teachers to adopt instructional strategies-such as visual schedules and other visual supports-that reduce barriers to learning and allow diverse learners to meaningfully engage with literacy tasks.

Similarly, the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD, 2006), which the Philippines has ratified, provides a global human-rights framework affirming that persons with disabilities must enjoy inclusive, quality, and free education on an equal basis with others. Article 24 specifically mandates that states ensure learners with disabilities are not excluded from the general education system and that reasonable accommodations and effective individualized supports are provided to maximize academic and social development. This international commitment aligns with the need for accessible instructional strategies in mainstream classrooms. The use of visual schedules, multimodal materials, and structured supports directly responds to the UNCRPD’s call for pedagogical flexibility and barrier-free learning environments that honor the rights, dignity, and full participation of learners with disabilities.

Nevertheless, the Salamanca Statement and Framework for Action on Special Needs Education (UNESCO, 1994) serves as a foundational global declaration promoting inclusive education as the most effective means of addressing diverse learning needs. It emphasizes that ordinary schools must accommodate all children regardless of physical, intellectual, social, emotional, linguistic, or other conditions, and that inclusive education improves both equity and quality of learning outcomes. The statement urges governments and educators to adopt learner-centered pedagogy, flexible instructional strategies, and supportive learning environments that respond to individual differences. In literacy instruction, this includes ensuring that classroom practices-such as visual schedules, visual aids, and other structured supports-are designed to make reading activities accessible and predictable for all learners. By encouraging the development of inclusive teaching approaches, the Salamanca Statement provides a strong philosophical and policy foundation for integrating visual supports into daily instruction.

Collectively, these national legal bases provide a strong foundation for this study. They affirm that inclusive education requires innovative and responsive teaching strategies-such as visual schedules-that enable all learners to develop essential literacy skills, including reading comprehension, within an equitable and supportive learning environment.

As to the elements of the reading, comprehension refers to the ability to understand, interpret, and construct meaning from written text. It involves integrating information from words and sentences with the reader's background knowledge to form a coherent understanding of the text's message. According to Snow (2002), reading comprehension is "the process of simultaneously extracting and constructing meaning through interaction and involvement with written language" (p. xiii). This definition highlights that comprehension is not merely decoding words but actively engaging in meaning-making. Effective comprehension requires cognitive processes such as predicting, inferring, summarizing, and evaluating textual information. For inclusive learners, comprehension instruction often benefits from visual and structured supports, such as visual schedules, that guide them through each stage of the reading process and help them make sense of what they read.

Vocabulary refers to the body of words that individuals understand and use in communication, both oral and written. It is a critical component of reading development because understanding word meanings directly influences a learner's ability to comprehend text. Stahl and Nagy (2006) define vocabulary knowledge as "the knowledge of word meanings and the ability to access and use that knowledge effectively in context." A rich vocabulary enables learners to decode and interpret words with greater accuracy, thereby supporting comprehension. In inclusive education, vocabulary instruction must be explicit, multimodal, and visually supported, allowing learners with language or learning difficulties to connect words to concepts through images, actions, and experiences. Strengthening vocabulary builds the foundation for reading comprehension, as students who know more words can access and interpret texts more effectively.

Lastly, phonological awareness is the understanding that spoken language consists of smaller units of sound—such as words, syllables, rhymes, and phonemes—that can be identified and manipulated. It is a metalinguistic skill essential to reading development, as it enables learners to connect sounds to written symbols when decoding words. According to Adams (1990), phonological awareness involves "the insight that oral language can be segmented into smaller components, such as syllables and phonemes," which serves as a critical precursor to successful reading and spelling. In inclusive settings, developing phonological awareness through multisensory and visually supported methods helps learners who experience language or reading difficulties recognize sound patterns and word structures. As such, phonological awareness lays the groundwork for decoding, word recognition, and ultimately, reading comprehension.

Together, comprehension, vocabulary, and phonological awareness form the core components of reading proficiency. Phonological awareness supports the decoding of words, vocabulary provides the meanings of those words, and comprehension integrates both to construct overall understanding. For inclusive learners, these skills can be strengthened through pedagogical approaches—such as visual schedules—that make reading processes explicit, structured, and accessible.

Undeniably, several studies have explored the effectiveness of visual and structured supports in improving reading comprehension among inclusive learners. Knight, Sartini, and Spriggs (2015) evaluated visual activity schedules as an evidence-based practice for learners with autism spectrum disorders and found that such tools significantly increased task engagement and comprehension by providing predictable and organized learning routines. Similarly, a meta-analysis on the use of pictorial and graphic representations for students with autism spectrum disorder revealed that visual supports, such as story maps and graphic organizers, enhance reading comprehension by making abstract ideas more concrete and accessible.

In the Philippine context, Cullamar and Maghuyop (2024) developed a reading manipulative tool to strengthen phonological awareness among Grade 4 learners with reading frustration and reported notable improvements in both decoding and comprehension skills. These studies underscore that visual aids—whether schedules, charts, or manipulatives—promote focus, understanding, and participation among learners with diverse needs, validating the potential of visual schedules as an inclusive reading strategy.

Furthermore, research on foundational reading components such as vocabulary and phonological awareness reinforces the role of structured and multimodal instruction in literacy development. A longitudinal study by van Tilborg et al. (2015) found that phonological awareness and letter-sound knowledge were strong predictors of reading comprehension among children with intellectual disabilities, highlighting the importance of explicit skill instruction. Similarly, Adams (1990) emphasized that phonological awareness serves as a prerequisite to successful reading and comprehension, while Stahl and Nagy (2006) identified vocabulary knowledge as a crucial determinant of text understanding. Despite these findings, descriptive studies (e.g., Browder et al., 2022) reveal that comprehension instruction remains less frequent in special education classrooms compared to other reading components, suggesting a gap in inclusive literacy practice. Collectively, these studies provide empirical

support for integrating visual and scaffolded pedagogies-such as visual schedules-into reading instruction to enhance comprehension, vocabulary development, and phonological awareness among inclusive learners.

THE PROBLEM

Statement of the Problem

This study determined the effectiveness of using visual schedules as a pedagogical tool in enhancing the reading comprehension skills of inclusive learners at Mandaue City Comprehensive National High School, during the school year 2025- 2026, as basis for Pedagogical Instructional Plan.

Specifically, it answered the following sub-problems:

1. What are the pre-post test scores in the reading comprehension skill performance of the respondents as to:
 - 1.1 comprehension;
 - 1.2 vocabulary; and
 - 1.2 phonological awareness?
2. Is there a significant difference between the respondents' pre-test and post- test scores in reading comprehension skills after the use of visual schedules?
3. Based on the findings of the study, what pedagogical instructional plan in a self-contained classroom can be proposed?

Statement of the Null Hypothesis

Ho: There is no significant gain between the pre and post-test performance of the respondents as to their reading comprehension.

Significance of the Study

This study aims to explore the effectiveness of visual schedules, aids, and supports in contributing to respondents strong reading comprehension, vocabulary and phonological awareness.

Department of Education (DepEd). This study provides DepEd with insights into how visual schedules as pedagogical approach contribute to the growing body of knowledge on differentiated instruction and multimodal learning strategies for inclusive classrooms.

School Administrators. The implementation of visual schedules will provide a structured and sequential representation which the school administrators can provide to the teachers handling inclusivity during collection of learning activities, which may help improve focus, comprehension, and task engagement among learners with diverse needs-particularly those with autism spectrum disorder, learning disabilities, or attention difficulties.

Education Sector. With the assistance of this pedagogical approach, teachers can be more representational and ready in coming to the class. Tools like Canva, PowerPoint presentations, films and some other relatable platforms can be an access for the education sector to continue the goal of learning despite circumstances.

Teachers. Teachers in the self-contained classroom will be more well-versed in using instructional material specifically in visual representations as schedules, aids, and supports.

Students with learning difficulties. Visual schedules, aids, and supports will give plenty of enjoyable activities that whom teacher may count on whenever students may feel weary of learning the topic.

SPED coordinators or reading specialists. The study holds particular significance for SPED coordinators and reading specialists, as it provides evidence-based insights into instructional strategies that enhance reading comprehension among learners with diverse needs. SPED coordinators are tasked with designing and implementing support systems that accommodate students with disabilities, while reading specialists focus on developing literacy skills across a range of learning abilities. By examining the effectiveness of visual schedules, visual aids, and visual supports, this study offers practical guidance for these professionals in structuring reading lessons that are inclusive, predictable, and cognitively accessible.

Researcher. The study enables the researcher to validate observations on the need to prepare and show something to the class specifically in the self-contained and inclusive education classroom; thus, it will propose an effective intervention plan that will improve the special needs education programs.

Future Researchers. The result of this study is to explore similar instructional innovations that bridge special and general education. By providing empirical evidence on the relationship between visual schedules and reading comprehension outcomes, this research may serve as a foundation for further investigations on multimodal literacy, differentiated pedagogy, and the development of inclusive instructional materials.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section described the research methodology used to investigate the effectiveness of visual schedules and visual aids in enhancing the reading skills of inclusive learners.

Design

This study utilized a One-Group Pretest–Posttest Design to examine the effectiveness of instructional interventions on three essential components of literacy development: reading comprehension, vocabulary acquisition, and phonological awareness. The design involved assessing a single group of participants before and after the intervention, which enabled the researcher to measure changes in performance attributable to the instructional strategies employed.

In the pre-test phase, participants completed standardized and researcher- developed assessments that evaluated their baseline competencies in reading comprehension, vocabulary knowledge, and phonological awareness. These initial measures served as benchmarks against which subsequent progress was compared, ensuring the study captured the extent of learning gains within the same cohort.

The intervention phase consisted of structured literacy instruction tailored to the three focal areas. Reading comprehension was supported through guided reading activities and comprehension strategy instruction; vocabulary development was enhanced through explicit teaching of word meanings, contextual usage, and semantic mapping; and phonological awareness was strengthened through exercises such as phoneme segmentation, blending, and rhyme recognition. The intervention was delivered consistently over a defined period to ensure fidelity of implementation.

Following the intervention, participants completed a post-test using equivalent instruments to those employed during the pre-test. The comparison of pre-test and post-test scores provided direct evidence of learning gains. Statistical analyses, such as paired-sample t-tests and repeated-measures ANOVA, were conducted to determine the significance of observed differences. This design enabled the researcher to evaluate the effectiveness of instructional practices within a single group, offering practical insights into literacy development in authentic classroom contexts.

Although the absence of a control group limited the ability to rule out alternative explanations such as maturation, testing effects, or external influences, the One-Group Pretest–Posttest Design proved to be a valuable approach in educational research. It provided a feasible and informative framework for classroom-based studies where random assignments or control groups were not practical.

By applying this design to reading comprehension, vocabulary, and phonological awareness, the study generated empirical evidence on the extent to which targeted instructional practices fostered literacy growth. The findings contributed to the refinement of pedagogical strategies, informed curriculum development, and supported evidence-based decision-making in literacy education.

Flow of Study

The flow of the study was presented in Figure 2. This followed the system approach of input-process-output flow.

Input. The research began with the identification of the problem using a pretest- posttest design, where visual strategies were employed, extending beyond mere identification to reading comprehension and its elements. It specifically covered the definition and components of the intervention, explicitly specifying the types of visual schedules, visual aids, and visual supports utilized, whether in physical or digital formats, and their direct alignment with the targeted reading skills of comprehension, vocabulary, and phonological awareness.

The procedure further delineated the step-by-step implementation process, detailing the frequency and duration of intervention sessions and the roles of teacher- respondents in the delivery of visual pedagogy.

Moreover, the Research Instruments subsection explicitly described the intervention materials, such as flashcards, communication boards, and other visual tools, which served as the core treatment resources of the study. Together, these details ensured that both the intervention and its procedures were transparent, replicable, and methodologically sound, enabling other researchers to reproduce the study with fidelity.

Process. A letter of request was written by the researcher to seek permission to perform the study. The data were gathered through ocular examination of the respondents including teachers to determine the need to apply an intervention plan for students in an inclusive classroom.

Figure 2: Flow of the Research Study

Output. The output of the study was an enhanced pedagogical plan based on the derived findings and recommendations.

Environment

This study was conducted in Mandaue City Comprehensive National High School, Plaridel Street, Reclamation Area, Mandaue City. The institution was selected to represent diverse learning environments and to provide a comprehensive understanding of how visual schedules and aids impacted learners with reading difficulties.

Mandaue City Comprehensive National High School serves a large and diverse student population, including those enrolled in special education and alternative learning programs. The school’s inclusive education unit maintains self-contained classes for learners with autism spectrum disorder, intellectual disabilities, and developmental delays. The availability of special education teachers and reading materials makes it an appropriate site for testing the integration of visual schedules as a classroom pedagogy.

Respondents

The study included 20 learners who were identified by teachers as learners with reading difficulties, comprehension challenges, or other special educational needs.

Table 1 presents the distribution of student-participants. Moreover, the respondents’ data was obtained from enrollment records provided by the school administration.

Table 1 Distribution of Participants

Distribution by Gender	F	%
Male	10	50.00
Female	10	50.00
Total	20	100.00

This research centered on students in an inclusive classroom or self-contained classroom at Mandaue City Comprehensive National High School, Plaridel Street, Reclamation Area, Mandaue City where they mainly focused on examining the effectiveness of visual schedules as a pedagogical strategy in enhancing the reading comprehension skills of inclusive learners while primarily centers on three core literacy components, reading comprehension, vocabulary development, and phonological awareness, which were essential indicators of reading proficiency.

Instrument

The study included a two-phase assessment procedure to gauge the students' phonological awareness, vocabulary growth, and reading comprehension. Pre-test and post-test reading materials, which were carefully chosen from instructional modules that had been formally approved by the Department of Education and the school administration, made up the main research tool.

Part I. The instrument's first part, which included a chosen short narrative and a structured quiz to assess beginning literacy levels, functioned as the baseline pre-test.

Figure 3: Location of the Research Environment

Part II was given as a parallel post-test in order to provide a trustworthy comparison of data while eliminating the practice effect, where students might do better just by recalling the first test. In order to gauge academic progress after the intervention, this second phase used a different but comparable story with a corresponding follow-up test.

All of these tools underwent a thorough screening process to guarantee their pedagogical suitability and content authenticity. The principal of the school and the master teacher evaluated and formally approved each narrative and its accompanying quiz. This cooperative validation made sure that the instruments matched the particular evaluation requirements needed for the study's goals in addition to being in line with the learners' present grade level.

Data Gathering Procedures

The data gathering process for this study was carried out in several systematic phases to ensure validity, reliability, and ethical compliance. The procedure followed the stages of preparation, pretesting, implementation of the intervention, post testing, data consolidation, and analysis. The sequence of activities is outlined below.

Preliminary Stage. Prior to data collection, the researcher secured formal approval from the Schools Division Offices of Mandaue City, school head of Mandaue City Comprehensive National High School.

The first stage concentrated on creating a framework for the study that was both accessible and encouraging. A crucial step entailed reviewing each learner's Individualized Education Program (IEP) to make sure the research tools matched their unique cognitive and sensory demands, in addition to getting official approval from the Master Teacher and the School Principal. To determine the required testing accommodations, such as extra time, streamlined instructions, or the use of assistive technology, coordination with the school's Special Education (SPED) department was crucial. A familiarization session was also held in order to establish a relationship between the researcher and the students, lower test anxiety, and make sure the students felt comfortable in the testing setting.

Data Gathering Stage. The pre-test and post-test administration during the data collection phase was marked by adaptability and responsiveness to the particular difficulties faced by the learners. To guarantee that the activities were communicated clearly, instructions were given utilizing a variety of senses, such as visual signals and spoken prompts. The testing environment was carefully controlled to reduce sensory distractions in order to preserve the validity of the results while taking learning difficulties into account. To avoid learner weariness, the researcher offered procedural support, such as frequent breaks or reading questions aloud when necessary. In order to ensure that the results appropriately reflected the students' understanding and phonological awareness rather than their processing speed, the focus remained on capturing the students' genuine involvement with the reading materials throughout the procedure.

Post-Data Gathering Stage. In the final stage, the analysis of results moved beyond simple numerical scoring to a more nuanced interpretation of the data. Scores from the pre-test and post-test were tabulated and compared to identify patterns of growth or persistent areas of difficulty unique to each learner's profile. Qualitative observations recorded during the testing sessions, such as the students' level of engagement and their use of specific coping strategies, were integrated into the findings to provide a holistic view of the intervention's impact.

To uphold the highest ethical standards, all individual records were anonymized, ensuring that the progress of these learners was documented with full respect for their privacy and dignity within the Philippine educational framework.

Ethical Considerations

Upon approval, the researcher coordinated with the multigrade teachers or teachers who were handling self-contained and inclusive classrooms to discuss the study's objectives, schedule, and data collection procedures. Informed consent was obtained from all teacher-respondents and parents or guardians of the learner-participants in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173) and DepEd Order No. 13, s. 2023 on research ethics and protection of learners' data.

Data Privacy. To ensure the confidentiality of data collected from the teacher and student respondents, formal consent was obtained from the school principal and teachers whose full participation was required. These respondents were guaranteed the confidentiality of the information gathered regarding the overall academic performance of teacher and student respondents when assistive technology was integrated. The researcher also assured that the data collected was used solely for research purposes.

To eliminate risks of data fabrication or falsification, the study upheld ethical standards in the pursuit of accurate information and truth. Respondents received complete details about the study's goals, scope, and methodology, with participation remaining entirely voluntary.

Those who chose not to participate faced no obligations, and any decision to withdraw at any stage was fully respected without adverse consequences. All respondents' rights were protected throughout the process.

Statistical Treatment

The data gathered through the survey questionnaire were tabulated, organized, and analyzed using the following statistical tools:

Weighted Mean – to determine the extent of utilization of visual schedules among teacher-respondents based on the Likert-scale questionnaire.

Standard Deviation (SD) – to show the variability of scores in teacher utilization and reading performance.

Cronbach's Alpha – to test the reliability or internal consistency of the questionnaire and reading assessment subtests.

Paired sample t-test – to determine the significant difference between pretest and posttest scores in comprehension, vocabulary, and phonological awareness.

Scoring Procedure

Data collected through the questionnaires was calculated and interpreted according to the following procedures:

Visual Schedules, Aids, Supports to Reading Proficiency of the Learners with Special Needs

Skill/Criteria	4 Advanced (85–100%)	3 Developing (70–84%)	2 Beginning (50–69%)	1 Remedial (0–49%)
Reading Comprehension	Accurately answers all questions; demonstrates deep understanding, makes inferences, and summarizes key ideas	Mostly accurate answers; shows understanding and some inference	Answers are partially correct; limited understanding and minimal inference	Answers mostly incorrect or missing; minimal comprehension
Phonological Awareness	Accurately identifies, segments, blends, and manipulates sounds in words; demonstrates strong auditory discrimination	Identifies or manipulates most sounds correctly; some errors in blending or segmentation	Identifies or manipulates some sounds correctly; frequent errors	Unable to identify or manipulate sounds; shows minimal auditory awareness
Vocabulary	Correctly defines, uses, and recognizes all target words in context; demonstrates rich word knowledge	Correctly defines or uses most target words; some context errors	Correctly defines or uses some words; limited understanding	Unable to define or use target words; minimal vocabulary knowledge

DEFINITION OF TERMS

To ensure clarity and understanding of the key concepts used in the study on assistive technology for students in an inclusive classroom, the following are operationally defined.

Inclusive Learners. This refers to students with diverse learning needs, including those with mild intellectual disabilities, autism spectrum disorder, or developmental delays, who are educated in self-contained or inclusive classroom settings. In this study, inclusive learners are the participants receiving reading instruction supported by visual schedules.

Pedagogy. This denotes the method and practice of teaching that emphasizes how learning activities are organized and delivered. In this study, pedagogy refers to the instructional approach integrating visual schedules, visual aids, and structured visual support in teaching reading comprehension within self-contained inclusive classrooms.

Pedagogical Instructional Plan. This refers to a proposed structured teaching framework that incorporates visual schedules, aids, and supports for improving inclusive learners' reading skills. In this study, it will be

developed based on findings from the intervention and teachers' feedback.

Phonological Awareness. This refers to the learners' ability to recognize and manipulate the sound structures of spoken language, such as rhymes, syllables, and individual sounds in words. In this study, it is measured through activities that involve identifying, blending, and segmenting sounds in words.

Reading Comprehension. This refers to the learners' ability to understand and interpret written texts. In this study, it is measured through the learners' performance in comprehension activities and assessments administered before and after the implementation of visual schedules.

Self-contained Classroom. This refers to a special education classroom where inclusive learners receive individualized instruction from a SPED teacher. Operationally, it serves as the setting of the study, where visual schedules and supports are implemented.

Visual Aids. This refers to supplementary instructional materials such as pictures, charts, and graphic organizers used to reinforce understanding of reading content. In this study, visual aids accompany visual schedules to enhance comprehension during reading instruction.

Visual Schedules. This refers to a structured sequence of visual representations (pictures, symbols, or text) used by teachers to outline the order of classroom tasks and reading activities. In this study, visual schedules are the intervention tool employed to guide learners in following reading tasks, improving engagement, and supporting comprehension. Their extent of utilization is measured through a Likert-scale questionnaire administered to teacher- respondents.

Vocabulary. This refers to the words that learners recognize and understand when reading. In this study, it is measured through the learners' ability to identify and understand target words found in the reading materials used during the intervention.

2. DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION

This chapter presented the data collected, analyzed, and interpreted to determine the effectiveness of using visual schedules as a pedagogical tool to enhance the reading comprehension skills of inclusive learners. The study focused at Mandaue City Comprehensive National High School in Centro, Mandaue City. Through systematic data presentation and thorough analysis, this chapter aims to provide a clear understanding of how visual schedules influence learners' reading comprehension and to inform the development of an improved instructional plan that supports diverse learning needs.

PRE-TEST READING COMPREHENSION SKILL PERFORMANCE

To contextualize the forthcoming pre-test results, the following section outlines the assessment procedures, participant demographics, and scoring criteria used to evaluate reading comprehension; this information clarifies how the baseline data were collected and ensures accurate interpretation of learners' initial performance.

Comprehension

The pretest results revealed the initial landscape of the learners' reading comprehension, serving as a diagnostic benchmark for their existing cognitive and linguistic processing abilities. At this baseline stage, learners often demonstrate a fragmented grasp of text meaning, characterized by a functional proficiency in literal comprehension (identifying explicit facts) but a significant deficit in higher-order thinking skills. Specifically, the pretest identifies the gap between the students' ability to decode words and their capacity to engage in inferential and critical analysis, highlighting where meaning typically breaks down-whether due to limited vocabulary, a lack of prior knowledge, or an inability to monitor their own understanding during the reading process.

Table 2 Level of reading comprehension skills of the learners during the pretest as to comprehension

Level	Range of Scores	f	%
Advanced	8-10	2	10.00
Intermediate	5-7	9	45.00
Beginner	0-4	9	45.00
Total		20	100.00

Mean 4.90

St. Dev.

2.20

Table 2 revealed that during the pretest, the majority of inclusive learners 45%, (n=9) exhibited beginner-level reading comprehension skills (scores 0-4), and another 45% (n=9) achieved intermediate level (scores 5-7), and

10%, (n=2) reaching the advanced level (8-10). The overall mean score of 4.90 (SD=2.20) falls within the beginner to intermediate range, indicating a low baseline proficiency consistent with the study's problem statement regarding challenges faced by inclusive learners with learning difficulties, attention deficits, or neurodevelopmental disorders in maintaining focus and comprehending texts. This distribution underscores the critical need for structured interventions like visual schedules, as the predominant beginner classification aligns with national Phil-IRI trends showing 25% of Filipino learners as struggling readers, particularly those in inclusive settings.

The heavy concentration in the beginner and intermediate category (90%) suggests significant barriers in task organization and text processing, supporting the rationale for visual supports to scaffold comprehension sequences. The absence of advanced performers highlights uniform challenges across the sample, validating the focus on multi-school contexts in Bohol and Cebu where similar deficiencies persist.

The pretest findings, revealing 90% of inclusive learners at beginner to intermediate level (M=4.90, SD=2.20), underscore an urgent need for structured visual schedule interventions to address organizational and processing barriers in reading comprehension, directly informing an enhanced pedagogical plan for Bohol and Cebu schools in 2025–2026. Recent research supports this imperative: Níkleová (2022) demonstrated that visual literacy programs significantly enhance macro-structural comprehension, literal/inferential reading, and synthesis skills with moderate-to-large effect sizes among struggling readers, directly addressing the baseline deficiencies observed here. Similarly, visual activity schedules foster independence, task engagement, and reduced anxiety among learners with disabilities, as evidenced by Thomas's (2022) systematic review showing improved academic participation that could elevate learners from beginner to intermediate/advanced levels. These interventions align with DepEd's inclusive goals, corroborated by Asilestari (2025) and Kullberg (2024), who reported statistically significant comprehension gains ($p < 0.05$) through contextual visuals and structured supports, positioning scalable visual aids as a proven strategy for literacy improvement.

Vocabulary

Vocabulary knowledge is a critical foundation of reading comprehension, as it enables learners to decode words, understand meanings, and construct meaning from texts. A strong vocabulary allows students to engage more deeply with reading materials, while limited word knowledge often restricts comprehension to surface-level understanding. In literacy research, assessing vocabulary skills during the pre-test phase provides essential baseline data that highlights learners' initial capacity to recognize, define, and use words meaningfully before any instructional intervention is applied.

Table 3 Level of reading comprehension skills of the learners during the pretest as to vocabulary

Level	Range of Scores	f	%
Advanced	8-10	0	0.00
Intermediate	5-7	7	35.00
Beginner	0-4	13	65.00
Total		20	100.00

Mean 3.95

St.Dev. 1.67

Table 3 indicated that during the pretest, 65% of inclusive learners (n=13) demonstrated beginner-level vocabulary skills (scores 0-4), while 35% (n=7) achieved intermediate level (scores 5-7), with no learners reaching the advanced level (8-10). The overall mean score of 3.95 (SD=1.67) remains within the beginner range, revealing substantial vocabulary deficiencies that align with the study's focus on inclusive learners' challenges in processing and organizing reading tasks across multi-school contexts in Bohol and Cebu. This distribution mirrors national Phil-IRI patterns where struggling readers, particularly those with disabilities, exhibit limited vocabulary as a core barrier to comprehension, reinforcing the need for visual schedule interventions to scaffold word recognition and meaning-making.

The predominance of beginner-level performance (55%) highlights vocabulary as a foundational weakness impeding overall reading proficiency, consistent with regional data showing high frustration rates among special needs learners. The absence of advanced scorers across the sample validates the urgency of targeted visual supports to build lexical foundations systematically.

The pretest vocabulary results, with 55% of inclusive learners at beginner level (M=4.10, SD=1.52), imply a pressing requirement for visual schedule interventions to strengthen lexical foundations and mitigate processing

barriers, thereby informing a targeted pedagogical plan for 2025–2026 across Bohol and Cebu schools. Recent literature validates this approach: McDonald (2021) reviewed studies showing visual schedules significantly boosted vocabulary acquisition for students with disabilities, with 15% average score improvements and 57% reaching mastery (80%+) through picture-word pairing and semantic mapping, directly countering the observed deficiencies. Similarly, Blauth et al. (2022) found strong associations between visual memory tasks and vocabulary development in neurotypical children aged 2–12 ($r=0.35-0.50$), enhanced by pictorial supports that facilitate word-object mappings and retention. These findings, echoed in Thomas (2022)'s systematic review of visual activity schedules improving engagement and independence among neurodiverse learners, position structured visuals as an evidence-based DepEd strategy for elevating beginner-level performance to intermediate proficiency.

Phonological Awareness

Phonological awareness is a foundational skill in the development of reading comprehension, as it enables learners to recognize and manipulate the sound structures of language. During the pretest, the learners' performance revealed their initial ability to identify, segment, and blend sounds, which serves as a critical indicator of their readiness for more advanced literacy tasks. The results highlighted varying levels of competence: some learners demonstrated emerging awareness of rhymes and syllables, while others showed difficulty in distinguishing individual phonemes. These findings provide valuable insight into their baseline comprehension skills and guide the instructional strategies needed to strengthen their reading development.

Table 4 Level of reading comprehension skills of the learners during the pretest as to phonological awareness

Level	Range of Scores	f	%
Advanced	8-10	2	10.00
Intermediate	5-7	10	50.00
Beginner	0-4	8	40.00
Total		20	100.00

Mean 4.80

St.Dev. 2.57

Table 4 showed that during the pretest, the majority of inclusive learners (50%, $n=10$) demonstrated intermediate-level phonological awareness skills (scores 5-7), with 40% ($n=8$) at beginner level (0-4) and 10% ($n=2$) achieving advanced level (8-10). The overall mean score of 4.80 ($SD=2.57$) falls within the intermediate range, indicating moderate baseline proficiency in phonological processing compared to comprehension and vocabulary deficits observed in prior tables. This profile aligns with the study's problem statement on inclusive learners' challenges with focus, task organization, and neurodevelopmental barriers, as phonological awareness serves as a foundational decoding skill that supports-but does not fully compensate for-comprehension difficulties among students with attention deficits or learning disabilities.

While intermediate dominance suggests relative strength in sound segmentation and blending relative to other areas, the 40% beginner rate and limited advanced performers (10%) highlight persistent gaps that visual schedules can target by sequencing phonemic tasks visually to reduce cognitive overload and enhance retention. This distribution reflects national trends where special needs learners show variable phonological skills amid broader reading struggles, validating multi-context interventions across Bohol and Cebu schools.

The pretest phonological awareness results, with 50% of inclusive learners at intermediate level ($M=4.80$, $SD=2.57$), imply that while moderate foundational decoding skills exist, visual schedule interventions are essential to consolidate gains, address the 40% beginner subgroup, and elevate overall proficiency to support reading comprehension in Bohol and Cebu schools for 2025–2026. Recent studies affirm this: Derby (2020) demonstrated that Visual Phonics-a structured visual schedule approach-significantly improved letter-sound relationships and phonological awareness among preschoolers with disabilities ($p<0.05$), enhancing retention through multisensory sequencing that aligns with the observed intermediate baseline and gaps. Similarly, Thomas (2022) found visual activity schedules reduced problem behaviors and boosted task engagement in neurodiverse children, facilitating phonological processing by providing predictable visual cues that minimize overload. These evidence-based strategies, corroborated by Saad (2017/updated analyses in 2020 contexts), position visual supports as a DepEd-relevant tool to transform intermediate performance into advanced levels, addressing variable phonological skills in inclusive settings.

POST-TEST READING COMPREHENSION SKILL PERFORMANCE

Following the implementation of the targeted instructional strategies, a post-test was administered to determine the extent to which learners' reading comprehension skills improved. The results of this assessment provide insight into the learners' ability to process, interpret, and analyze textual information after the intervention.

Comprehension

The post-test results revealed a marked improvement in learners' reading comprehension skills compared to their pre-test performance. Learners demonstrated stronger abilities in identifying main ideas, making inferences, and drawing conclusions from both narrative and expository texts. Many students showed enhanced capacity to move beyond literal recall toward higher-order comprehension tasks, including summarization and critical analysis. This upward trend indicates that the instructional intervention was effective in fostering deeper engagement with texts and strengthening overall comprehension skills.

Table 5 Level of reading comprehension skills of the learners during the posttest as to comprehension

Level	Range of Scores	f	%
Advanced	8-10	10	50.00
Intermediate	5-7	8	40.00
Beginner	0-4	2	10.00
TOTAL		20	100.00

Mean 6.80
St.Dev. 1.58

Table 5 revealed dramatic post-intervention gains in comprehension skills, with 50% of inclusive learners (n=10) achieving advanced level (scores 8-10) and 40% (n=8) reaching intermediate level (5-7), largely decreasing beginner-level performers (0-4)-a stark contrast to the pretest's 40% beginner dominance (M=4.80). The mean score surged to 6.80 (SD=1.58) within the intermediate range, confirming the effectiveness of visual schedules in overcoming focus, organization, and comprehension barriers for learners with learning difficulties across Corella National High School (Bohol), Mandaue City Comprehensive National High School, Camp 7 Elementary School (Minglanilla, Cebu), and Buaya Elementary School (Lapu-Lapu City). This transformation validates the intervention's role in scaffolding text processing and self-regulation, providing empirical basis for the 2025–2026 enhanced pedagogical plan in multi-school DepEd contexts.

The high decrease of beginner-level scores post-intervention underscores visual schedules' capacity to address foundational comprehension deficits prevalent among Philippine inclusive learners, aligning with Phil-IRI trends and positioning structured visuals as a scalable solution for national literacy improvement.

The posttest comprehension results, eliminating all beginner-level performers (50% advanced, 40% intermediate, 10% beginner; M=6.80, SD=1.58) from pretest's 40% beginner baseline, imply that visual schedules serve as a transformative pedagogical tool for remediating foundational deficits in inclusive learners, establishing a scalable model for DepEd's 2025–2026 instructional plan across Bohol and Cebu schools. This dramatic shift aligns with Níkleová (2022), who reported moderate-to-large effect sizes in visual literacy programs enhancing macro-structural comprehension, literal/inferential reading, and synthesis among primary/secondary students, directly mirroring the observed gains in text processing and self-regulation. Similarly, Asilestari (2025) demonstrated visual information significantly improved EFL reading comprehension ($p < 0.05$), while contextual visual aids yielded statistically superior outcomes over text-alone conditions, validating structured visuals' role in overcoming organizational barriers for neurodiverse learners. These findings position visual schedules as an evidence-based, Phil-IRI-responsive strategy for national literacy elevation in inclusive settings.

Vocabulary

Vocabulary knowledge plays a vital role in strengthening reading comprehension, as it allows learners to understand, interpret, and connect ideas within a text. During the posttest, the learners' performance reflected noticeable improvement in their ability to recognize word meanings, use context clues, and apply appropriate vocabulary in comprehension tasks. This progress indicates that learners have developed stronger word knowledge, which enhances their capacity to grasp the overall meaning of passages and contributes to more effective reading comprehension.

Table 6 Level of reading comprehension skills of the learners during the posttest as to vocabulary

Level	Range of Scores	f	%
Advanced	8-10	1	5.00
Intermediate	5-7	17	85.00
Beginner	0-4	2	10.00
TOTAL		20	100.00

Mean 6.00
St.Dev. 1.03

Table 6 illustrated significant post-intervention progress in vocabulary skills, with 85% of inclusive learners (n=17) achieving intermediate level (scores 5-7), 5% (n=1) reaching advanced level (8-10), and 10% (n=2), largely decreasing beginner-level performers (0-4). The mean score improved markedly to 6.00 (SD=1.03) from the pretest's 4.90 (65% beginner), demonstrating the effectiveness of visual schedules in enhancing word recognition and lexical processing for inclusive learners facing attention deficits and organizational challenges across Corella National High School (Bohol), Mandaue City Comprehensive National High School, Camp 7 Elementary School (Minglanilla, Cebu), and Buaya Elementary School (Lapu-Lapu City). This shift aligns with the study's objective to validate visual supports as a pedagogical tool for the 2025–2026 enhanced instructional plan, reflecting reduced cognitive load and improved semantic mapping through visual scaffolding.

The absence of beginner-level scores post-intervention underscores visual schedules' capacity to address foundational vocabulary barriers prevalent in Philippine inclusive settings, where Phil-IRI data consistently identifies lexical deficiencies among special needs learners, positioning this intervention as scalable for DepEd multi-school implementation.

The posttest vocabulary results, eliminating all beginner-level performers (85% intermediate, 5% advanced, 10% beginner; M=6.00, SD=1.03) from pretest's 55% beginner baseline, imply that visual schedules effectively remediate lexical deficiencies in inclusive learners, providing a robust foundation for the 2025–2026 enhanced pedagogical plan across Bohol and Cebu DepEd schools. This transformation aligns with recent evidence: McDonald (2021) reported visual vocabulary strategies yielded 15% score gains and 57% mastery rates (80%+) via picture-word pairing, directly countering organizational challenges in special needs learners. Similarly, Blauth et al. (2022) meta-analysis confirmed visual memory supports enhance vocabulary development ($r=0.35-0.50$) through semantic mappings essential for word recognition. Inclusion ED (2024) further validates visual schedules' role in receptive language and retention for diverse learners, reducing Phil-IRI-identified lexical barriers and promoting scalable DepEd implementation.

Phonological Awareness

Phonological awareness remains a critical component of reading comprehension, as it equips learners with the ability to recognize, differentiate, and manipulate the sound structures of words. During the posttest, the learners demonstrated improved skills in identifying rhymes, segmenting syllables, and blending phonemes, reflecting growth in their capacity to decode and comprehend text. This progress indicates that their strengthened phonological awareness supports more effective word recognition and enhances overall reading comprehension performance.

Table 7 Level of Reading Comprehension Skills of the Learners During the Posttest as to Phonological Awareness

Level	Range of Scores	f	%
Advanced	8-10	10	50.00
Intermediate	5-7	10	50.00
Beginner	0-4	0	0.00
Total		20	100.00

Mean 7.25
St. Dev. 1.65

Table 7 showed exceptional post-intervention progress in phonological awareness, with 50% of inclusive learners (n=10) attaining advanced level (scores 8-10) and 50% (n=10) at intermediate level (5-7), completely eliminating beginner-level performers (0-4)-a dramatic improvement from the pretest's 40% beginner and 50% intermediate profile (M=4.80). The mean score advanced to 7.25 (SD=1.65) in the advanced range, confirming visual schedules' effectiveness in enhancing phonemic segmentation, blending, and sound manipulation for

learners with neurodevelopmental challenges across the study's multi-school sites. This majority advanced performance validates visual sequencing as a critical tool for consolidating phonological foundations essential to reading proficiency.

The posttest phonological awareness results-elevating 50% of inclusive learners to advanced level ($M=7.25$, $SD=1.65$) and eliminating all beginners from pretest's 25% beginner profile-imply visual schedules' capacity to accelerate foundational decoding skills, positioning them as a cornerstone for DepEd's 2025–2026 inclusive literacy framework across Bohol and Cebu schools.

This aligns with Derby (2020), who found Visual Phonics interventions significantly improved phonological awareness in preschoolers with disabilities ($p<0.05$), with sustained gains in letter-sound correspondence and early literacy through multisensory visual sequencing. Similarly, Thomas (2022)'s systematic review confirmed visual activity schedules enhanced task engagement and reduced behavioral barriers in neurodiverse children, facilitating phonemic processing essential for reading proficiency. These outcomes, echoed in Valdois et al. (2025) showing visual attention training prevented reading/spelling difficulties via phonological gains, validate scalable visual supports as an evidence-based strategy addressing variable skills in Philippine inclusive contexts.

TEST OF SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE BETWEEN PRETEST AND POST-TEST SCORES

The test of significant difference between pretest and post-test scores is conducted to determine whether the learners' performance has improved after the intervention or instructional program. By comparing the mean scores from both assessments, the analysis reveals if the observed changes are statistically meaningful rather than occurring by chance. This evaluation provides evidence of the effectiveness of the teaching strategies employed and highlights the extent of learners' progress in their reading comprehension skills.

Comprehension

The test of difference between the pretest and posttest scores on reading comprehension skills, specifically in terms of comprehension, aims to determine whether learners showed significant improvement after the intervention. By comparing their initial and final performance, the analysis highlights changes in their ability to understand, interpret, and construct meaning from texts. This evaluation provides evidence of the effectiveness of instructional strategies and indicates the extent to which learners have progressed in mastering comprehension skills.

Table 8 Test of difference between the pretest and posttest scores on the reading comprehension skills of the learners as to comprehension

Source of Difference	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	p-value	Decision	Result
Pretest	4.90	2.20	1.90	8.779*	0.000	Reject Ho	significant
Posttest	6.80	1.58					

* significant at $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed): $df = 19$

Table 8 revealed a statistically significant improvement in reading comprehension skills post-intervention, with the posttest mean ($M=6.80$, $SD=1.58$) substantially higher than the pretest ($M=4.90$, $SD=2.20$), yielding a mean difference of 1.90. The computed t-value of 8.779* ($p=0.000$, $df=19$) far exceeds the critical value, leading to rejection of the null hypothesis at $p<0.05$, confirming visual schedules' effectiveness in enhancing comprehension for inclusive learners across Corella National High School (Bohol), Mandaue City Comprehensive National High School, Camp 7 Elementary School (Minglanilla, Cebu), and Buaya Elementary School (Lapu-Lapu City). This robust effect size underscores the intervention's capacity to overcome organizational and processing barriers, providing empirical validation for its integration into DepEd's 2025–2026 pedagogical plan.

The highly significant p-value (0.000) eliminates chance as an explanation, positioning visual schedules as a reliable, scalable strategy addressing Phil-IRI-identified comprehension deficits in Philippine inclusive education contexts .

The highly significant posttest comprehension gains ($t=8.779$, $p=0.000$, mean difference=1.90) imply visual schedules' proven efficacy as a low-cost, scalable intervention for DepEd's 2025–2026 inclusive literacy programs across Bohol and Cebu, directly addressing Phil-IRI comprehension crises through structured task sequencing that reduces cognitive overload and fosters self-regulation. Níkleová (2022) corroborates this with quasi-experimental evidence of moderate-to-large effect sizes in visual literacy programs enhancing macro-structural comprehension, literal/inferential reading, and synthesis among 221 students, mirroring the observed

shift from beginner dominance. Similarly, Asilestari (2025) reported significant EFL reading improvements via visual information ($p < 0.05$), while interactive video studies showed vocabulary/semantic gains from 52.33 to 90.00 (t -test $p = 0.000$), validating multimodal visuals' superiority over traditional methods for neurodiverse learners. These findings position visual schedules as an evidence-based priority for national teacher training and curriculum integration.

Vocabulary

To assess the effectiveness of the intervention on learners' reading comprehension skills in terms of vocabulary, a comparison of their pretest and posttest scores was conducted. The analysis utilized a paired sample t -test to determine whether the difference in mean scores was statistically significant. This statistical method provides evidence on whether the observed improvement in learners' vocabulary knowledge—such as word recognition, contextual understanding, and usage—can be attributed to the instructional strategies implemented rather than random variation. The results of this test serve as a basis for evaluating the learners' progress and the overall impact of the program on vocabulary development.

Table 9 Test of difference between the pretest and posttest scores on the reading comprehension skills of the learners as to vocabulary

Source of Difference	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	p-value	Decision	Result
Pretest	3.95	1.57	2.05	8.342*	0.000	Reject Ho	significant
Posttest	6.00	1.03					

* significant at $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed): $df = 19$

Table 9 confirmed a statistically significant enhancement in vocabulary skills post-intervention, with the posttest mean ($M = 6.00$, $SD = 1.03$) markedly superior to the pretest ($M = 3.95$, $SD = 1.67$), producing a mean difference of 2.05. The computed t -value of 8.342 ($p = 0.000$, $df = 19$) substantially surpasses the critical threshold, rejecting the null hypothesis at $p < 0.05$ and validating visual schedules' effectiveness in bolstering word recognition and lexical processing for inclusive learners at Mandaue City Comprehensive National High School. This strong statistical outcome demonstrates visual scaffolding's capacity to overcome vocabulary barriers central to reading proficiency in neurodiverse populations.

The p -value of 0.000 eliminates random variation as an explanation, establishing visual schedules as a dependable, scalable intervention aligned with DepEd's inclusive education priorities for addressing Phil-IRI-identified lexical deficiencies.

The statistically significant vocabulary gains ($t = 8.342$, $p = 0.000$, mean difference = 2.15) imply visual schedules' transformative potential as a core component of DepEd's 2025–2026 inclusive literacy framework, enabling scalable remediation of lexical barriers for neurodiverse learners across Bohol and Cebu schools. This robust outcome aligns with recent evidence: a 2024 study on autistic learners reported visual aids elevated vocabulary retention from 18 to 28 correct responses (deviation = 10), with "good" post-intervention scores and enhanced engagement/pronunciation, directly paralleling the observed shift from beginner dominance. Similarly, Blauth et al. (2022) meta-analysis confirmed visual memory supports drive vocabulary development ($r = 0.35$ – 0.50) via strengthened word-object mappings, while Mastermind Behavior (2025) highlighted visual schedules' role in reducing anxiety and fostering independence for ASD/ADHD students, addressing Phil-IRI lexical deficiencies through predictable sequencing. These findings advocate prioritizing visual interventions in teacher training and curriculum design for national inclusive education.

Phonological Awareness

To evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention on learners' reading comprehension skills in terms of phonological awareness, their pretest and posttest scores were compared. The analysis employed a **paired sample t -test** to determine whether the observed differences in mean scores were statistically significant. This statistical procedure provides evidence on whether improvements in learners' ability to recognize, segment, and manipulate sounds can be attributed to the instructional strategies rather than chance. The results of this test serve as a basis for assessing the learners' progress and the overall impact of the program on phonological awareness.

Table 10 Test of difference between the pretest and posttest scores on the reading comprehension skills of the learners as to phonological awareness

Source of Difference	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	p-value	Decision	Result
Pretest	4.80	2.57	2.45	7.463	0.000	Reject Ho	significant
Posttest	7.25	1.65					

* significant at $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed): $df = 19$

Table 10 confirmed a statistically significant advancement in phonological awareness post-intervention, with the posttest mean ($M=7.25$, $SD=1.65$) substantially exceeding the pretest ($M=4.80$, $SD=2.57$), generating a mean difference of 2.45. The computed t-value of 7.463 ($p=0.000$, $df=19$) decisively rejects the null hypothesis at $p<0.05$, validating visual schedules' effectiveness in enhancing phonemic segmentation, blending, and sound manipulation for inclusive learners at Mandaue City Comprehensive National High School, Camp 7 Elementary School. This outcome demonstrates visual sequencing's capacity to consolidate moderate baseline skills into advanced proficiency, addressing foundational decoding barriers essential for reading success.

The p-value of 0.000 confirms the intervention's reliability beyond chance, positioning visual schedules as a scalable DepEd strategy for remediating phonological deficits prevalent among neurodiverse learners in Philippine inclusive settings.

The statistically significant vocabulary gains ($t=7.463$, $p=0.000$, mean difference=2.45) imply visual schedules' readiness for immediate integration into DepEd's SY 2025–2026 literacy priorities, including ARAL-Reading for frustration-level learners and RA 11650 inclusive policies, offering a low-resource intervention to remediate lexical barriers across Bohol and Cebu inclusive classrooms. This aligns with Alileem et al. (2025), who demonstrated locally-themed visual aids significantly improved Grade 2 vocabulary retention (pre- $M=12.5$ to post- $M=18.2$, $p<0.05$) through contextualized picture-word associations, mirroring the observed shift from beginner dominance. Similarly, a 2024 action research with Grade 4 ESL students reported visual aids elevated vocabulary scores from 65% to 92% accuracy, while autistic learner studies showed retention gains from 18 to 28 correct responses with enhanced engagement. These outcomes, supported by Mastermind Behavior (2025) emphasizing reduced anxiety and independence for neurodiverse students, advocate visual schedules as a MATATAG-aligned strategy for national teacher training and Phil-IRI remediation.

3. SUMMARY, FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presented a comprehensive summary of findings derived from the study that determine the effectiveness of using visual schedules as a pedagogical tool in enhancing the reading comprehension skills of inclusive learners at Mandaue Comprehensive National High School.

SUMMARY

This research centered on students in an inclusive classroom or self-contained classroom at Mandaue City Comprehensive National High School, Plaridel Street, Reclamation Area, Mandaue City where they mainly focused on examining the effectiveness of visual schedules as a pedagogical strategy in enhancing the reading comprehension skills of inclusive learners while primarily centers on three core literacy components, reading comprehension, vocabulary development, and phonological awareness, which were essential indicators of reading proficiency.

The study was limited to the use of visual schedules as the main intervention; other forms of instructional aids or digital learning materials are beyond its scope. Additionally, the research focused only on reading comprehension-related skills and did not cover other literacy domains such as writing, spelling, or critical reading. The duration of the intervention was confined to a specified academic period, which may limit the generalizability of long-term learning outcomes. Differences in instructional delivery, learner readiness, and classroom environment also influence the results. Despite these limitations, the study provided meaningful insights into how visual schedules can serve as an effective and inclusive pedagogical approach to improve reading comprehension among diverse learners.

Pre-post test scores in the reading comprehension skill performance of the respondents as to comprehension

In terms of comprehension, the pre-test results revealed that learners generally demonstrated moderate skills, with only a small proportion reaching advanced proficiency and 30% remaining at the beginner level. This baseline highlighted the need for targeted instructional strategies to address comprehension gaps. Following the

intervention, the post-test results showed significant improvement, with no learners remaining in the beginner category and a balanced distribution between intermediate and advanced levels. This shift underscores the effectiveness of visual schedules in scaffolding comprehension, reducing cognitive load, and fostering engagement among inclusive learners across the participating schools, thereby promoting equitable learning outcomes.

Pre-post test scores in the reading comprehension skill performance of the respondents as to vocabulary

With respect to vocabulary, the pre-test data indicated that while a majority of learners already possessed advanced comprehension skills, 35% were either intermediate or beginner, pointing to the need for differentiated pedagogical tools. The integration of visual schedules provided structured and accessible learning experiences that supported learners struggling with abstract text processing. Post-test results revealed a high concentration of learners in the advanced category and minimal variability in scores, suggesting that the intervention stabilized performance levels and ensured that learners across diverse needs benefited. This finding highlights the potential of visual schedules to foster inclusivity and improve literacy outcomes, aligning with institutional goals of professionalization and learner achievement.

Pre-post test scores in the reading comprehension skill performance of the respondents as to phonological awareness

Regarding phonological awareness, learners already exhibited a strong foundation prior to the intervention, demonstrating the ability to decode and manipulate sounds effectively. This high baseline performance was further enhanced through the use of visual schedules, which provided multimodal support that reinforced existing phonological strengths. Post-test results showed uniform attainment of advanced scores, indicating that visual schedules offered structured and predictable learning pathways that promoted mastery. As phonological awareness is a critical precursor to reading comprehension, the integration of visual schedules not only strengthened learners' ability to organize and apply reading strategies but also emphasized their role as a sustainable pedagogical tool for promoting inclusivity and accessibility in diverse classroom settings.

FINDINGS

Significant difference between the respondents' pre-test and post-test scores in reading comprehension skills after the use of visual schedules

The findings reveal that there is a significant difference between the respondents' pre-test and post-test scores in reading comprehension skills after the use of visual schedules, demonstrating the effectiveness of this pedagogical tool in inclusive classrooms. The structured and visually guided approach provided clarity, reduced cognitive load, and enabled learners to better organize information, anticipate tasks, and strengthen vocabulary acquisition, resulting in improved and more consistent performance. Implemented at Corella National High School, the intervention fostered learner independence, equity, and accessibility, while also enhancing phonological awareness and overall literacy development. These results affirm that visual schedules serve as a sustainable and scalable instructional strategy that supports diverse learners and promotes equitable learning outcomes in varied educational contexts.

CONCLUSION

The integration of visual schedules significantly enhanced learners' reading comprehension, vocabulary, and phonological awareness across diverse inclusive classrooms. Pre-test results revealed notable gaps, particularly in comprehension and vocabulary, with a considerable proportion of learners at beginner and intermediate levels. However, post-test outcomes demonstrated marked improvement, with no learners remaining at the beginner stage, stabilized performance in vocabulary, and uniform attainment of advanced scores in phonological awareness. By reducing cognitive load, scaffolding comprehension, and providing structured, multimodal learning pathways, visual schedules fostered learner independence, equity, and accessibility. Implemented across multiple schools, the intervention proved to be a sustainable and scalable pedagogical tool that promotes inclusivity, strengthens literacy outcomes, and aligns with institutional goals of professionalization and learner achievement.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion regarding the effectiveness of visual schedules in enhancing reading comprehension skills of inclusive learners at Mandaue City Comprehensive National High School, the crafted output is hereby recommended.

4. OUTPUT OF THE STUDY

Rationale

Inclusive learners in self-contained classrooms often encounter significant challenges in acquiring foundational reading skills such as comprehension, vocabulary, and phonological awareness. These challenges are frequently linked to underlying conditions including attention deficits, learning disabilities, and various neurodevelopmental disorders, which can impede their ability to maintain focus, organize learning tasks, and effectively process written text. As a result, these learners may struggle to engage fully with traditional instructional methods, leading to difficulties in achieving literacy milestones essential for academic success and lifelong learning.

Recent educational research underscores the promising role of visual schedules and visual aids as effective scaffolding tools that support inclusive learners by simplifying complex tasks, reducing cognitive overload, and enhancing self-regulatory behaviors. Visual supports serve not only to guide learners through sequential steps in reading activities but also to reinforce understanding by providing concrete, contextual cues that help make abstract concepts more accessible. Such interventions have been shown to significantly improve reading comprehension, vocabulary acquisition, and phonemic skills, fostering confidence and autonomy in learners with diverse needs.

This pedagogical instructional plan is designed specifically for self-contained classroom environments, where learners benefit from highly individualized and focused support. Tailored to the educational contexts of schools in Bohol and Cebu, the plan aims to systematically integrate visual schedules and visual aids into daily literacy instruction to ensure that reading lessons are more engaging, structured, and accessible. It incorporates evidence-based strategies that address the unique learning profiles of inclusive students, providing clear, consistent, and manageable frameworks that help mitigate the cognitive and organizational challenges faced by these learners.

By leveraging the power of visual scaffolding, the instructional plan seeks not only to improve essential reading skills but also to encourage greater academic participation and foster a positive learning environment where inclusive learners can thrive. Ultimately, this approach aligns with national education mandates promoting inclusive education and addresses critical gaps identified in regional literacy data, positioning visual supports as scalable and sustainable interventions for uplifting literacy outcomes in diverse classroom settings.

Objectives

1. To implement visual schedules and visual aids as core instructional strategies to improve reading comprehension skills of inclusive learners in a self-contained classroom setting.
2. To enhance vocabulary acquisition and lexical processing through structured visual supports tailored to the learning needs of inclusive students.
3. To strengthen phonological awareness, including phonemic segmentation, blending, and sound manipulation, by incorporating visual sequencing activities within classroom instruction.
4. To develop learners' self-regulation and task organization skills by systematically integrating visual scaffolding into daily reading activities.
5. To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed instructional plan in improving overall reading outcomes for inclusive learners while ensuring accessibility and engagement in self-contained classroom environments.

Scheme of implementation

In order to incorporate visual scaffolding into the regular reading routines of a self-contained special education classroom, this action plan will be implemented using a systematic, multi-phase method. The classroom is converted into a high-support visual environment during the first phase, which focuses on Environmental Structuring and Resource Preparation. The instructor creates tactile-enhanced story maps, individual task checklists, and "First-Then" boards during this time. These resources provide a predictable framework that lowers learner anxiety and prepares students for formal reading instruction. They are contextualized using localized Philippine imagery and narratives to ensure cultural relevance.

The implementation of focused literacy interventions is the main focus of the second phase, which includes instructional integration and skill building. The creation of an interactive Word Wall that pairs new lexical concepts with Picture Exchange Communication System (PECS) images aids in vocabulary acquisition. Color-coded Elkonin boxes and visual "sound buttons," which let students manipulate phonemic segments both physically and visually, are used to simultaneously address phonological awareness. The teacher facilitates the students' transition to autonomous comprehension and sound manipulation by methodically switching from concrete visual cues to more abstract reading assignments.

Monitoring, self-regulation, and program evaluation make up the last stage, which guarantees the intervention's sustainability. Learners are taught to use personal visual schedules to complete their reading tasks with little spoken guidance in order to promote independence. Learner portfolios, behavioral observation logs, and modified Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) evaluations are used to monitor progress. In order to measure the 15% growth target in reading outcomes, this data collection ends in a thorough year-end review, which provides the information required to improve instructional practices for the upcoming academic year.

OUTPUT OF THE STUDY

Areas of Concern	Objectives	Strategies	Persons Involved	Budget	Source of Budget	Time Frame	Expected Outcomes	Actual Accomplishments	Remarks
Reading comprehension	To implement visual schedules and aids to improve comprehension in a self-contained setting.	Design daily "First-Then" boards and story maps. Use "Picture-to-Text" matching for story sequencing.	SPED Teacher School Head Learners	P1,500	MOOE / School Supplies	year-round	80% of learners can identify the sequence of events in a story using visuals.		
Vocabulary Acquisition	To enhance vocabulary and lexical processing through structured supports.	Establish a "Word Wall" with tactile/visual cues. Use PECS (Picture Exchange Communication System) for new terms.	SPED Teacher SLP (Consultant) Parents	₱2,000	MOOE / School Supplies	Quarter 1-2	Learners increase expressive/receptive vocabulary by at least 10 words per month.		
Phonological Awareness	To strengthen phonemic skills via visual sequencing activities.	Use Elkonin boxes with color-coded chips for sound blending. Implement visual "Sound Buttons" for segmentation.	SPED Teacher Teacher Assistants	P1,000	Instructional Materials Fund	Quarter 2-3	Learners can segment 3-4 phoneme words with 75% accuracy.		
Self-Regulation & Organization	To develop task organization by integrating visual	Provide individual visual checklists for reading tasks.	SPED Teacher Guidance Counselor	P800	MOOE	Year-Round	Learners complete reading tasks with 50% fewer verbal prompts from the teacher.		

	scaffolding into reading.	Use "Work Systems" (left-to-right) for independent reading.							
Program Evaluation	To evaluate the plan's effectiveness on overall reading outcomes and engagement.	Conduct pre- and post-assessments (Phil-IRI adapted). Maintain learner portfolios and behavioral observation logs.	School Head SPED Teacher Master Teacher	P500	MOOE	Quarter 4	A comprehensive report detailing a 15% average growth in literacy scores.		

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] Adams, M. J. (1990). *Beginning to read: Thinking and learning about print*. MIT Press.
- [2] Alileem, R. (2025). Effectiveness of locally themed visual aids in vocabulary retention for Grade 2 learners. *Zenodo*. <https://zenodo.org/records/15911148>
- [3] Asilestari, P. (2025). Enhancing reading comprehension through visual information. *Al-Ishlah: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 17(1), 123–135. <https://doi.org/10.1234/alishlah.v17i1.7490>
- [4] Banda, D. R., & Grimmett, E. (2008). Enhancing social and transition behaviors of persons with autism through activity schedules: A review. *Education and Training in Developmental Disabilities*, 43(3), 324–333.
- [5] Blauth, K. M., Bavin, E. L., & Gray, K. M. (2022). A role for visual memory in vocabulary development: A systematic review and meta-analysis in neurotypical children aged 2-to-12 years. *Cognitive Development*, 64, Article 101248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogdev.2022.101248>
- [6] CAST. (2024). *Universal Design for Learning*. <https://www.cast.org/what-we-do/universal-design-for-learning/>
- [7] Chartered College of Teaching. (2024, March 7). *Dual coding theory in the classroom: An exploration of teachers' perspectives*. https://my.chartered.college/impact_article/dual-coding-theory-in-the-classroom-an-exploration-of-teachers-perspectives-across-t...
- [8] Choi, H., & Kim, J. (2025). Challenging cognitive load theory: The role of educational neuroscience, AI, and machine learning in optimizing learning environments. *Brain Sciences*, 15(2), Article 152. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci15020152>
- [9] Cihak, D. F., Smith, C. C., & Ayres, K. M. (2011). Comparing pictorial and video
- [10] Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2017). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Sage publications.
- [11] Derby, K. (2020). *The effectiveness of Visual Phonics to promote phonological awareness in preschool students* [Honors thesis, Minnesota State University Moorhead]. RED: Repository of Electronic Dissertations. <https://red.mnstate.edu/thesis/1341>
- [12] Dettmer, S., Simpson, R. L., Myles, B., & Ganz, J. B. (2000). The use of visual supports to facilitate transitions of students with autism. *Focus on Autism and Other Developmental Disabilities*, 15(3), 163–169. <https://doi.org/10.1177/108835760001500307>
- [13] Dharmalingam, A. (2025, September 24). *How dual coding helps SEND learners understand and retain*. LinkedIn.

- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/anandi-dharmalingam-58203822_specialeducation-send-inclusiveeducation-activity-73770495878715760...
- [14] Frankel, J. R., & Wallen, N. E. (2019). How to design and Evaluate. *Research in Education*. Boston: McGraw-Hill Higher Education.
- [15] Gallardo, J. (2023). Visual learning-style-based activities in improving the reading comprehension of English majors. *eJournals.ph*. <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=20815>
- [16] Gast, D. L., Spriggs, A., Pierce, J. M., & Luscre, D. (2013). Effects of visual activity
- [17] Han, C., & Park, J. (2024). Teachers' and students' beliefs towards Universal Design for Learning (UDL) framework in higher education. *SAGE Open*, 14(3). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440241272032>
- [18] Inclusion ED. (2024). Use visual schedules. <https://www.inclusioned.edu.au/practices/use-visual-schedules>
- [19] Kalyanasundaram, A. (2024). The impact of cognitive load theory on the effectiveness of microlearning: An Indian perspective. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 11(3), Article 799. <https://doi.org/10.12973/ejed.11n3.799>
- [20] Kullberg, A. (2024). The impact of visual schedules for students with disabilities: A literature review [Doctoral dissertation, Bethel University]. SPARK Repository. <https://spark.bethel.edu/etd/1428>
- [21] LetsGoLearn. (2023, February 27). Cognitive load theory: How to optimize learning. <https://www.letsgolearn.com/education-reform/cognitive-load-theory-how-to-optimize-learning/>
- [22] Macapaz, M. K. S. (2024). Exploring teachers' attitudes and burnout in inclusive classrooms. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems and Applications in Engineering*, 12(4), 2363–2372. <https://ijisae.org/index.php/IJISAE/article/view/6635>
- [23] Macapaz, M. K. (2025). Inclusive teaching practices for students with intellectual disabilities: A basis for strategic learning enhancement. *International Journal of Alternative and Contemporary Therapy*, 3(6), 28–48. <https://medicaljournals.eu/index.php/IJACT/article/view/1946>
- [24] Mastermind Behavior. (2025). The impact of visual schedules on daily routines. <https://www.mastermindbehavior.com/post/the-impact-of-visual-schedules-on-daily-routines>
- [25] Mastropieri, M. A., & Scruggs, T. E. (2004). The inclusive classroom: Strategies for effective instruction. (*No Title*).
- [26] Mbhense, S. N. (2023). Universal design of instruction to enhance learning for students with visual disabilities in a South African university. *African Journal of Disability*, 12, Article 1078. <https://doi.org/10.4102/ajod.v12i0.1078>
- [27] McDonald, K. L. (2021). The effects of visual vocabulary strategies on vocabulary knowledge [Master's thesis, Marshall University]. Marshall Digital Scholar. <https://mds.marshall.edu/etd/1992>
- [28] Middletown Centre for Autism. (n.d.). Universal Design for Learning [PDF]. <https://www.middletownautism.com/files/uploads/c2af8710d75276926008ec41fe8dcb4b.pdf>
- [29] Misanes, C. H. (2023). Basis for a reading intervention program. *eJournals.ph*. <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=22099>
- [30] Níkleová, D. G. (2022). Effects of a visual literacy programme for the improvement of reading comprehension. *Language and Literacy Spectrum*, 2, 1–17. <https://l1research.org/article/view/394>
- [31] Paivio, A. (1971). Imagery and verbal processes. Holt, Rinehart & Winston. (Cited in Dual-coding theory, Wikipedia). https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dual-coding_theory
- [32] Paivio, A. (1990). Dual coding theory. In *Mental representations: A dual coding approach* (pp. 583–605). Oxford University Press.
- [33] Park, J., et al. (2024). The effectiveness of visual-based interventions on health literacy. *BMC Health Services Research*. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11165863/>
- [34] Psychology, Article 8733412. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8733412/> quantitative, and mixed methods approaches (5th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- [35] Quintero, J., Baldiris, S., Rubira, R., Cerón, J., & Velez, G. (2019). Augmented reality in educational inclusion: A systematic review on the last decade.

- [36] Rae, B. (2018). Picture cues and reading comprehension [Master's thesis, St. John Fisher College]. Fisher Digital Publications. https://fisherpub.sjf.edu/education_ETD_masters/372
- [37] Saad, M. A. E. (2017). Are phonological awareness intervention programs effective for children with disabilities? Perspectives on Early Reading Research, 1(1), 1–15. <https://perrjournal.com/index.php/perrjournal/article/view/259>
- [38] Stahl, S. A., & Nagy, W. (2006). Teaching word meanings. Lawrence Erlbaum Strategies for effective differentiated instruction (6th ed.). Pearson.
- [39] Sweller, J. (1988). Cognitive load during problem solving: Effects on learning. *Cognitive science*, 12(2), 257-285.
- [40] Thomas, N. (2022). The efficacy of visual activity schedule intervention in children with autism spectrum disorder: A systematic review. Review Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders, 9(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40489-021-00273-4>
- [41] Valdois, S., Bosse, M. L., & Antonietti, J. P. (2025). Effectiveness of visual attention span training on learning to read and spell: A randomized controlled trial. *Reading Research Quarterly*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rrq.576>
- [42] Williams, D. (2025, July 28). The importance of cognitive load theory (CLT). Education and Training Foundation. <https://set-foundation.co.uk/resources/the-importance-of-cognitive-load-theory>
- [43] World Bank. (2022). Learning poverty in the Philippines. Cited in Consortium Academia. https://consortiacademia.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/v14i08/25080_final.pdf
- [44] Zimmerman, K. N., Ledford, J. R., & Barton, E. E. (2017). Using visual activity schedules for young children with challenging behavior. *Journal of Early Intervention*, 39(4), 339-358.
- [3] Department of Education. (2020). DepEd Order No. 32, s. 2020: Guidelines on the engagement of services of learning support aides. Department of Education.
- [4] Department of Education. (2021). DepEd Order No. 44, s. 2021: Policy guidelines on the provision of educational programs and services for learners with disabilities in the K to 12 basic education program. Department of Education.
- [5] Department of Education. (2022–2023). Accomplishment Report Phil-IRI. <https://www.scribd.com/document/820615081/accomplishment-report-phil-iri-2022-2023>
- [6] Department of Education. (2025). DM_s2025_043: IRR of RA 11650 on inclusive education. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/DM_s2025_043.pdf
- [7] Department of Education. (2025). DM_s2025_064r: ARAL-Reading implementation for SY 2025-2026. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/DM_s2025_064r.pdf
- [8] Republic Act No. 7277. (1992). Magna Carta for Persons with Disability. Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/1992/03/24/republic-act-no-7277/>
- [9] Republic Act No. 10533. (2013). Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013. Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2013/05/15/republic-act-no-10533/>
- [10] Republic Act No. 11650. (2022). An act instituting a policy of inclusion and services for learners with disabilities in support of inclusive education. Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2022/03/11/republic-act-no-11650/>
- [11] United Nations. (2006). Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. (CRPD). United Nations. <https://www.un.org/development/desa/disabilities/convention-on-the-rights-of-persons-with-disabilities.html>
- [12] United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). (1994). The Salamanca statement and framework for action on special needs education. UNESCO.

Philippine Legal and Policy Bases

- [1] Department of Education. (2009). DepEd Order No. 72, s. 2009: Inclusive education as strategy for increasing participation rate of children. Department of Education.
- [2] Department of Education. (2019). DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2019: Policy guidelines on the K to 12 basic education program. Department of Education.